

Conventional and Novel Solubility Enhancement Techniques: An Updated Review

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ABSTRACT

Poor aqueous solubility always remains a major challenge in the preparation and development of oral drug delivery systems, as it directly involves and influences the dissolution rate, absorption, and bioavailability. A significant ratio of newly discovered drug molecules reveals low water solubility, particularly those belonging to BCS Class II and IV, requiring the use of new effective solubility enhancement strategies. Conventional approaches like pH adjustment, use of cosolvents, hydrotrophy, particle size reduction, micronization, solid dispersions, complexation, eutectic systems, and micellar solubilization are widely used for particle size reduction and solubility enhancement. In addition to this, advanced and emerging techniques including nanosizing, nanosuspensions, supercritical fluid processing, sonocrystallization, ultra-rapid freezing, solvent deposition, and hot-melt extrusion are highlighted for their potential to enhance dissolution behaviour and oral bioavailability. The role of polymeric carriers and surfactants in stabilizing drug particles, avoiding recrystallization, and improving the wettability also emphasized in this selected topic. This review not only provides a comprehensive overview of both conventional and novel techniques employed to improve the solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs but also focuses on the importance of choosing a suitable solubility enhancement method based on the physicochemical properties of the drug and formulation requirements, thereby aiding in the rational design of effective pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Keywords: Solubility enhancement, hydrotrophy, low solubility, novel carriers

INTRODUCTION

Solubility is defined as the amount of solute that dissolves in a given amount of solvent at a specific temperature. It is expressed as percentage (%), molar strength(mol/lit), molal strength, molar ratio components, volume fraction. In order to form a homogenous system solid gets dissolved in liquid phase, and this phenomenon is known as solubility [1]. Thus, the techniques available for enhancing the aqueous solubility acts as a significant tool to increase efficiency and reduce side effects of drug. The type of solvent used, temperature and pressure play a fundamental role in determining the solubility of a drug. Solubility in a selected solvent is defined by the saturated concentration, beyond which extra solute remains undissolved, and the solution concentration remains unchanged.

Solubility is maintained when the rate of dissolving equals the rate at which the solid reforms, resulting in dynamic equilibrium. Under some specific conditions, a solution is able to hold more solute than its equilibrium solubility allows, forming a metastable supersaturated system. A drugs *in-vivo* absorption is majorly determined by its solubility and permeability; there are various strategies to enhance or to modify these properties. Several methods are present to enhance the solubilization of medications with low aqueous solubility, thereby promoting better bioavailability [2]. The orally administered drugs achieve complete absorption only when they possess adequate solubility in the gastric environment, which in turn supports better bioavailability. Bioavailability is majorly influenced by multiple parameters, with the most critical being the drug's solubility in aqueous fluids and its ability to permeate lipid-based biological membranes. particle size reduction,

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chemical modification, pH adjustment, formation of solid dispersions, complexation, use of cosolvents, micellar solubilization, hydrotropic methods, and other related techniques are common approaches used to enhance drug solubility. Only the drug that is dissolved can pass through biological membranes and enter systemic circulation. Therefore, the drug should be present as a water based medium at the absorption site for the occurrence of absorption.

The BCS predicts the class of drug on the basis of its aqueous solubility and permeability. It was introduced

in 1995 by Amidon and his colleagues. It is a scientific framework which is used to classify drug substances on the basis of three key properties: aqueous solubility, intestinal permeability, and dissolution rate [3]. In simple terms, the BCS explains how well a drug dissolves in body fluids and how easily it can pass through the intestinal lining and get absorbed into the bloodstream. This system is frequently used to predict oral drug absorption and to support the development and evaluation of pharmaceutical dosage forms[4].

Table 1: BCS classification of selected drugs

Class	Solubility	Permeability	Example
Class-I	High	High	Metoprolol, Propranolol, Chloroquine
Class -II	Low	High	Nifedipine, Phenytoin, Ketoconazole
Class -III	High	Low	Cimetidine, Metformin, Captopril
Class -IV	Low	Low	Taxol, Clorthiazole, Furosemide

Significance of solubility in pharmaceutical formulations

The oral administration is the most commonly used route for the delivery of drugs due to its ease of administration, high patient compliance, cost-

effectiveness, minimal sterility constraints, and also flexibility in dosage form strategy.

The major issue in designing oral dose forms is their low solubility. Low bioavailability is primarily due to inadequate solubility and permeability.

Table 2: B.P. and U.S.P. solubility criteria

Descriptive terms	Parts of solvent required to dissolve one part of solute
Very soluble	Less than 1
Freely soluble	More than 1 but less than 10
Soluble	More than 10 but less than 30
Sparingly soluble	More than 30 but less than 100
Slightly soluble	More than 100 but less than 1000
Very slightly soluble	More than 1000 but less than 10,000
Very slightly soluble or practically Insoluble	More than 10,000

Process of solubilization

Solubilization takes place through a sequence of events:

- The intermolecular or ionic bonds within the solute are disrupted.

- The solvent molecules move apart to create space for the solute
- The solute particles interact with and become surrounded by the solvent molecules[5].

Factor affecting the solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs

The solubility of a solid is determined by its physical form, the type and composition of the solvent medium, particle size, temperature, pressure, the nature of the solute and solvent, molecular size, polarity, polymorphs, and solution rate[6,7,8].

Nature of the solute and solvent

At room temperature, only about 1 gm of lead (II) chloride dissolves in 100 gm of water, where as 200 gm of zinc chloride can dissolve in the equal amount of water. This large contrast in solubility arises from fundamental differences in the inherent properties of the two compounds.

Molecular size

When the size or molecular weight gets increased, its solubility generally decreases. Larger molecules are harder for solvent molecules to surround and solvate. In organic compounds, enhanced carbon branching increases their solubility because branching reduces the overall volume of the molecule, making it easier for solvent molecules to interact with and solvate it.

Polarity

In general, non-polar solutes dissolve in non-polar solvents, whereas polar solutes dissolve in polar solvents. Polar molecules contain both positive and negative ends. After the solvent is also polar, the positive end of the solvent is attracted to the negative end of the solute. This attraction is an intermolecular force called a dipole–dipole interaction.

pH

The pH of a substance is closely related to its pKa and the proportion of the drug present in its ionized and unionized forms. This relationship is described by the Henderson–Hasselbalch equation:

$$\text{pH} = \text{pKa} + \log [A^-/\text{HA}]$$

Here, pKa represents the dissociation constant of the substance. When the pH of the medium moves away from the pKa value at which the drug exists equally in ionized and unionized forms, the degree of ionization changes. This change in ionization alters the solubility of the substance due to formation of additional intermolecular interactions, mainly ionic attraction forces, which improve its interaction with water.

Solubility enhancement techniques

Fig 1. Solubility enhancement techniques

Fig 1. Various techniques of solubility enhancement

pH Adjustment

Poorly water-soluble drugs that contain ionizable groups such as basic groups that can be protonated or acidic groups that can be deprotonated can often be dissolved in water through adjusting the pH of the medium. In principle, pH adjustment can be applied to both oral and parenteral dosage forms. However, in the case of intravenous administration, there is a risk of drug precipitation because blood has a strong buffering capacity and maintains a pH of about 7.2–7.4. Therefore, when using this approach, it is important to estimate the buffer capacity of the formulation and the tolerability of the selected pH. For oral administration, drug solubility is also influenced by changes in pH as the drug moves through the gastrointestinal tract. The stomach has a highly acidic pH of around 1–2, while the pH in the duodenum ranges from approximately 5 to 7.5. As a result, the extent of drug solubility may vary at different sites in the intestine. This approach is most suitable for ionizable compounds that remain stable and soluble after pH adjustment. According to the pH-partition hypothesis and the Henderson–Hasselbalch equation, the degree of ionization of a drug depends on the pH of the surrounding medium and the pKa of the drug[8].

Use of cosolvents

One of the most common and effective approaches to enhance the solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs is the use of co-solvents. In this method, a water-miscible or partially miscible organic solvent is added to the aqueous system to enhance drug solubility. This process, known as cosolvency, works by reducing the interfacial tension between the aqueous medium and the hydrophobic drug, thereby facilitating better drug dissolution. Commonly used co-solvents include polyethylene glycol (PEG 300), propylene glycol, and ethanol. Co-solvent-based preparations are widely used and can be administered through oral as well as parenteral routes [8]. For example, the solubility of co-trimoxazole can be improved by using a combination of propylene glycol and water. Similarly, paracetamol is formulated as an elixir by dissolving it in a combination of alcohol, propylene glycol, and syrup, which helps enhance its solubility and stability[9].

Hydrotropy method

Hydrotropy is a simple and effective method used to improve the water solubility of poorly soluble drugs. In this method, a large amount of another substance, called a hydrotropic agent, is added to the solution. These hydrotropic agents are usually ionic organic salts and are highly soluble in water. When present in

sufficient concentration, they help the drug dissolve better in the aqueous medium[10].

Some salts or additives increase the solubility of a drug in a solvent, a process known as “salting in,” while others reduce solubility, which is called “salting out.” In hydrotropy, salts containing large and highly water-soluble ions promote the salting-in effect, especially for drugs that are non-electrolytes[11]. This phenomenon, where non-electrolyte drugs show increased solubility in the presence of hydrotropic agents, is referred to as hydrotropism. Overall, hydrotropy enhances drug solubility by improving the interaction between the drug molecules and water, making it a useful technique for formulating poorly water-soluble drugs[12]. Rofecoxib solubility was improved by using hydrotropes like urea and nicotinamide[13].

Precipitation Method

In the precipitation method, a poorly water-soluble drug, such as cyclosporine, is initially dissolved in a suitable organic solvent. This drug solution is then rapidly mixed with a non-solvent, usually water, which causes the drug to precipitate out as very fine particles in the nanometer range. The dispersion formed by this process is often referred to as a

hydrosol[14]. In this technique, the drug solution is inserted into water, which acts as the bulk solvent. During injection, the water must be stirred efficiently so that rapid mixing occurs and the drug precipitates uniformly as nanocrystals rather than forming large particles. These nanocrystals can then be separated from the liquid by filtration and dried to obtain the final product[15]. This method has been successfully used to prepare nanosuspensions of drugs such as danazol and naproxen, leading to improved dissolution rates and enhanced oral bioavailability.

Particle Size Reduction

Micronization

Particle size plays a crucial role in drug bioavailability, as reducing particle size increases surface area and enhances dissolution rate. Micronization improves drug dissolution primarily through surface area enhancement and is commonly achieved using milling techniques such as jet mills and colloid mills. However, the drug's saturation solubility does not get altered by this approach and it is less suitable for high-dose drugs. Currently, micronization and nanosuspension are the main techniques employed for particle size reduction to improve drug dissolution [16].

Fig 3. Micronization techniques

Supercritical fluid process

Supercritical fluids (SCFs), particularly carbon dioxide, are widely used as solvents because they can dissolve non-volatile compounds above their critical temperature and pressure, where they exist as a only homogeneous phase. SCFs exhibit properties intermediate between gases and liquids, making them useful for processing and formulation applications [17].

Adjacent the critical point, minor changes in temperature or pressure cause significant variations in density and transport properties such as viscosity and diffusivity, as well as physicochemical properties like polarity [18]. Common supercritical solvents include carbon dioxide, water, ethanol, ammonia, nitrous oxide, ethylene, propylene, and n-pentane. Various SCF-based techniques, including RESS, antisolvent precipitation methods, SEDS, polymer impregnation, and aerosol-based processing, have been developed

for particle formation and drug delivery applications [19].

Nanosizing

In order to improve oral bioavailability and dissolving rate, particularly for poorly soluble medications, nanosizing is a process that reduces drug particle size to the submicron range (≈ 100 – 250 nm) to increase dissolution rate and oral bioavailability, especially for poorly soluble drugs. Advanced milling and high-pressure homogenization technologies allow for the consistent synthesis of drug nanoparticles. Elan's NanoCrystal® wet milling and SkyePharma's Dissocubes® high-pressure homogenization are two common techniques that use mechanical attrition and cavitation forces to convert crystalline drug particles into nanoparticles [20]. Nanoparticles are stabilized with surfactants or polymers to avoid aggregation, resulting in nanosuspensions that can then be administered into traditional dosage forms such as tablets or capsules. Nanoformulations considerably increase solubility rates and supplement existing bioavailability-boosting technologies such as solid dispersions and surfactant systems. Nanosizing is especially effective for BCS Class II and IV drugs with dissolution rate-limited absorption. Nanosizing has shown clinically successful in products such as sirolimus, fenofibrate, aprepitant, and megestrol acetate. Overall, nanosizing is a promising and well acknowledged method for increasing the oral bioavailability of poorly soluble medicines, and it is becoming important in the creation of fast-dissolving oral dosage forms.

Ultra-rapid freezing

A new cryogenic technique which is known as ultra-rapid freezing that produces nano-structured drug particles with significantly enhanced surface area. Depending on the solvent system and progression parameters, the method can make particles with different morphologies. In order to produce extremely porous, agglomerated particles, this process involves freezing a drug that has been dissolved in an aqueous solution of anhydrous polymer water onto the surface of a cryogenic substrate with a thermal conductivity (k) between 10 and 20 W/(m K). The solvent was removed by collecting frozen particles. The polymer acts as a

stabilizer and inhibits the development of crystals. The URF method has the ability to produce powders with excellent physicochemical qualities, comparable to those produced by other rapid freezing technologies, due to rapid conductive heat transfer, which leads to high super-saturation and nucleation rates.

Similar to previous freezing techniques, the drug/polymer combination must be rapidly frozen in order to avoid phase separation during freezing, which permits the active molecularly disseminated with the polymer. Like to controlled precipitation, this technique is rapid and scalable then it makes use of common process equipment, pharmaceutically approved solvents, and excipients. High glass-transition temperature (T_g) polymers, like PVP or HPMC, prevent the drug from recrystallizing. This method can be used extensively to improve the BCS class-II drugs in vivo absorption.

Solvent deposition

Reduction of particle size is a well-established technique for improving the dissolution rate of drugs. However, when hydrophobic drugs are micronized, they often tend to aggregate or form clumps when they come into contact with the dissolution medium, which can limit the expected improvement in dissolution [21]. To overcome this problem, Sekiguchi and Obi suggested incorporating poorly water-soluble drugs as microcrystalline or molecular dispersions within a solid matrix made of water-soluble carriers. This approach helps enhance both the dissolution rate and absorption of the drug. For example, a poorly water-soluble drug such as nifedipine can be dissolved in an organic solvent like alcohol and then placed onto an inert, hydrophilic solid carrier such as starch, resulting in improved drug dissolution.

Nano suspension

A therapeutic nanosuspension is a biphasic system consisting of drug particles in the nanometer size range that are stabilized using suitable surfactants [22]. These formulations are designed for various routes of administration, including oral, topical, parenteral, and pulmonary delivery. In nanosuspensions, the solid drug particles generally

have an average particle size between 200 and 600 nanometers, with the overall particle size distribution usually remaining below 1 micron [23].

- Bottom-up technology
- Top-down technology

These are the two methods most commonly used for the preparation of nano suspensions

Micellar Solubilization

Micellar solubilization is a method used to improve the solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs by using surfactants. Due to their amphiphilic nature, surfactant molecules naturally arrange themselves into organized structures called micelles when present above a certain concentration [24]. These micelles have a hydrophobic core and a hydrophilic outer surface. Poorly soluble or water-insoluble drugs become trapped within the hydrophobic core of the micelles, which allows them to remain dispersed in the aqueous medium and thereby increases their apparent solubility. The formation of micelles occurs only when the surfactant concentration reaches a specific level known as the critical micelle concentration (CMC). Surfactants with lower CMC values form more stable micelles [25]. Examples of drugs that are commonly solubilized using this approach include repaglinide, rosiglitazone, glyburide, and glimepiride

Sono crystallization

This method is used to increase the solubility and dissolution of hydrophobic medications and investigate its effect on the drugs crystal characteristics [26]. It is known as cutting-edge particle engineering. Ultrasound has also been successfully used to decrease particle size by the recrystallization of poorly soluble materials employing liquid solvents and antisolvents. Sono crystallization induces crystallization using ultrasonic power with a frequency range of 20–100 kHz. Ultrasound in the 20 kHz–5 MHz range is used in the majority of applications [27].

Solid Dispersion

It is a formulation approach which was introduced by Sekiguchi and Obi to maximize the dissolution and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs. The term “solid dispersion” refers to a system in which one or more active drug substances are dispersed uniformly in an inert carrier in the solid state. These systems are generally prepared by using methods such as the melting (fusion) method, solvent evaporation method, or a combination of both. Over time, the definition has extended to include drug dispersions in polymers prepared using various techniques, including certain nanoparticles, microcapsules, and microspheres [28]. Here in this method, a poorly soluble drug is dispersed within a highly water-soluble, hydrophilic solid matrix. This arrangement advances drug dissolution by improving contact between the drug and the dissolution medium. Solid dispersions may exist as eutectic mixtures, where the drug and carrier are mixed at a non-molecular level, or as solid solutions, where the drug is molecularly dispersed within the carrier [29].

Carriers Used in Solid Dispersions

Acids: Citric acid, tartaric acid, succinic acid

Sugars: Sucrose, dextrose, sorbitol, maltose, galactose, xylitol

Polymeric materials: Polyvinylpyrrolidone, PEG 4000 and 6000, carboxymethyl cellulose, hydroxypropyl cellulose, guar gum, xanthan gum, sodium alginate, dextrin, cyclodextrin

Surfactants: Polyoxyethylene stearate, poloxamer, deoxycholic acid, Tweens and Spans, Gelucire 44/14, vitamin E TPGS NF

Miscellaneous: Urea, urethane, hydroxyalkyl xanthene, pentaerythritol [30].

Surface-active agents which used as carriers plays an important role in solid dispersions. These substances, even at low concentrations, adsorb onto the surfaces or interfaces thereby reducing surface or interfacial tension. They possess both hydrophilic and hydrophobic regions within the same molecule and are therefore described as amphiphilic in nature [31].

Methods of Solid Dispersions

By dispersing poorly soluble medications in a hydrophilic carrier, solid dispersion is an efficient way to improve their solubility and oral bioavailability. Solid dispersions are prepared and assessed using a variety of techniques

Hot Melt (Fusion)

This Method involves physically mixing the medication with a water-soluble carrier and heat the mixture until it melts. To create a solid dispersion appropriate for tablet formation, the molten mixture is quickly cooled, consolidated, crushed, and sieved. The drug and carrier must be thermally stable and miscible in the molten state for the preparation to be successful [32]

Solvent Evaporation Method

To create a solid dispersion, the medication and carrier are dissolved in a common volatile solvent, which is subsequently evaporated under low pressure. This technique is appropriate for medications that are sensitive to heat and prevents thermal deterioration. Nevertheless, disadvantages include probable solvent-related stability problems, increased expense, and challenges with total solvent removal [33].

Hot melt extrusion

A modified fusion technique called "hot melt extrusion" uses an extruder to accomplish strong mixing. Better content consistency, continuous processing, and appropriateness for large-scale production are all made possible by it. One of the limitations is that high shear and temperature may cause heat-sensitive medications to degrade [34].

Co-evaporation/co-precipitation

This method is especially helpful for weakly basic medications that precipitate in the pH of the intestines, reducing their bioavailability. By preventing drug precipitation in the intestinal environment and preserving solubility, the use of appropriate carriers and polymers enhances bioavailability and permits regulated medication release.

Mechanism of Increased Dissolution Rate in Solid Dispersions

Solid dispersions improve drug dissolution through several mechanisms. Those include reduction in effective particle size, solubilization of the drug by using the carrier, improved wettability and dispersibility, and the formation of metastable dispersions with reduced lattice energy, which allows quicker dissolution. For example, the dissolution energy of furosemide alone is about 17 kcal/mol, whereas in a 1:2 furosemide-PVP co-precipitate, it is reduced to approximately 7.3 kcal/mol, resulting in improved dissolution behaviour.

Complexation

Complexation refers to the association of two or more molecules to form a non-covalently bonded entity with a definite stoichiometric ratio. In pharmaceuticals, complexation is commonly used to improve the aqueous solubility of drugs. The two main types of complexation useful for this purpose are stacking (self-association) and complexation [35].

Self-association and Stacking Complexation

Non-polar parts of drug molecules tend to avoid contact with water because water molecules strongly interact with each other through hydrogen bonding. As a result, these non-polar regions come together, leading to aggregation of the molecules to reduce their exposure to water. This behavior is especially common in molecules that contain large, flat, non-polar regions. When similar molecules associate with each other, the process is called self-association, whereas association between different molecules is referred to as stacking complexation. These stacked complexes may be formed between identical or different molecules.

Inclusion Complexation

Inclusion complexes are designed when a non-polar molecule, or the non-polar part of a molecule known as the guest, fits into the non-polar cavity of another molecule or group of molecules called the host. When the guest molecule enters the host cavity, the interaction between water and the non-polar regions of both molecules is reduced, leading to increased solubility. [36] This inclusion phenomenon occurs due to the same driving force responsible for micelle formation, self-association, and stacking, namely the

tendency of non-polar regions to be excluded from water [37]. Among the various host molecules, cyclodextrins are the most commonly used for

forming inclusion complexes in pharmaceutical formulations.

Fig 4. β -cyclodextrin with 7 glucose units

Eutectic Systems

A eutectic system consists of two compounds that mix completely with each other in the molten or liquid state but show very limited solubility in one another when they are in the solid state. It is prepared by melting the two components together to form a uniform liquid and then rapidly cooling the melt so that it solidifies[38].

On cooling, the components recrystallize separately, but they remain very finely and intimately mixed at a

microscopic level [39]. Although each compound retains its own crystalline structure, the close mixing makes the system behave differently from a simple physical mixture. Thermodynamically, a eutectic system represents an intimate mixture of the two crystalline components, which often results in a lower melting point and improved dissolution characteristics compared to the individual compounds [40].

Fig 5. Eutectic systems

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CONCLUSION

Since poor water solubility directly impacts dissolution, absorption, and bioavailability, it is a

significant problem in the development of many drug formulations. To get around this restriction, a number of conventional and cutting-edge solubility enhancement methods have been developed. Each technique uses a different mechanism to increase the solubility. The physicochemical characteristics of the medication, the necessary dosage form, and the mode

of administration all influence the choice of an appropriate technique. All the solubility enhancement techniques are essential for increasing the therapeutic efficacy of medications that are poorly soluble in water and greatly aid in the development of successful pharmaceutical formulations.

REFERENCES

1. Akhgari A, Shakib Z, Sanati S. A review on electrospun nanofibers for oral drug delivery. *Nanomed J.* 2017;4(4). doi:10.22038/nmj.2017.04.001
2. Deshmukh AS, Tiwari KJ, Mahajan VR. Solubility enhancement techniques for poorly water-soluble drugs. *Int J Pharm Sci Nanotechnol.* 2017;10(8):3701–3708. doi:10.37285/ijpsn.2017.10.3.1
3. Nainwal N, Singh R, Jawla S, Saharan VA. The solubility-permeability interplay for solubility-enabling oral formulations. *Curr Drug Targets.* 2019;20(14):1434–1446. doi:10.2174/1389450120666190412165549
4. Chavda H, Patel C, Anand I. Biopharmaceutics classification system. *Syst Rev Pharm.* 2010;1(1):62. doi:10.4103/0975-8453.59514
5. Agarwal S, Gupta GD, Chaudhary S. Solid dispersion as an eminent strategic approach in solubility enhancement of poorly soluble drugs. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.* 2010;1:1–13. doi:10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.1(8-S).1-13
6. Jagtap S, Magdum C, Jadge D, Jagtap R. Solubility enhancement technique: a review. *J Pharm Sci Res.* 2018;10(9):2205–2211
7. Ting JM, Porter WW III, Mecca JM, Bates FS, Reineke TM. Advances in polymer design for enhancing oral drug solubility and delivery. *Bioconj Chem.* 2018;29(4):939–952. doi:10.1021/acs.bioconjchem.7b00646
8. Amin K, Dannenfelser RM, Zielinski J, Wang B. Lyophilization of polyethylene glycol mixtures. *J Pharm Sci.* 2004;93(9):2244–2249. doi:10.1002/jps.20047
9. Doke VV, Kunwarpuriya AS, Gupta K, Khutle NM. Co-solvency and anti-solvent method for the solubility enhancement: an overview. *World J Pharm Res.* 2020;9(5):584–600
10. Nidhi K, Indrajeet S, Khushboo M, Gauri K, Sen DJ. Hydrotrophy: a promising tool for solubility enhancement. *Int J Drug Dev Res.* 2011;3(2):26–33
11. Yadav NK, Shukla T, Upmanyu N, Pandey SP, Khan MA. Novel application of mixed hydrotropic solubilization technique in the formulation and evaluation of solid dispersion of flupirtine maleate. *J Drug Deliv Ther.* 2018;8(5):481–488
12. Rasool AA, Anwar AH, Lewis WD. Solubility enhancement of some water-insoluble drugs in the presence of nicotinamide and related compounds. *J Pharm Sci.* 1991;80(4):387–393. doi:10.1002/jps.2600800414
13. Namdev B, Venkatachalam S, Jawahar N, Chorsiya A. A brief review on solubility enhancement technique: hydrotrophy. *Indian J Pharm Educ Res.* 2022;56(2):347–355
14. Gupta P, Kakumanu VK, Bansal AK. Stability and solubility of celecoxib–PVP amorphous dispersions: a molecular perspective. *Pharm Res.* 2004;21(10):1762–1769. doi:10.1023/B:PHAM.0000045232.34547.22
15. Jagtap S, Magdum C, Jadge D, Jagtap R. Solubility enhancement technique: a review. *J Pharm Sci Res.* 2018;10(9):2205–2211
16. Kale AR, Kakade S, Bhosale A. A review on: solubility enhancement techniques. *J Curr Pharm Res.* 2020;10(2):3630–3647
17. Bin LK, Janakiraman AK, Abd Razak FS, Uddin AH, Sarker MZI, Ming LC, Goh BH. Supercritical fluid technology and its pharmaceutical applications: a revisit with two decades of progress. *Indian J Pharm Educ Res.* 2020;54:s1–s3
18. Abuzar SM, Hyun SM, Kim JH, Park HJ, Kim MS, Park JS, Hwang SJ. Enhancing the solubility and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs using supercritical antisolvent (SAS) process. *Int J Pharm.* 2018;538(1–2):1–13. doi:10.1016/j.ijpharm.2017.12.033
19. Campardelli R, Baldino L, Reverchon E. Supercritical fluids applications in nanomedicine. *J Supercrit Fluids.* 2015;101:193–214. doi:10.1016/j.supflu.2015.03.014
20. Kumar LA, Pattnaik G, Satapathy BS, Swapna S, Mohanty D. Targeting to brain tumor: nanocarrier-based drug delivery platforms, opportunities, and challenges. *J Pharm Bioallied*

- Sci. 2021;13(2):172–177. doi:10.4103/jpbs.JPBS_239_20
21. Bhalani DV, Nutan B, Kumar A, Singh Chandel AK. Bioavailability enhancement techniques for poorly aqueous soluble drugs and therapeutics. *Biomedicines*. 2022;10(9):2055. doi:10.3390/biomedicines10092055
22. Chopra H, Bibi S, Islam F, Ahmad SU, Olawale OA, Alhumaydhi FA, Marzouki R, Baig AA, Emran TB. Emerging trends in the delivery of resveratrol by nanostructures: applications of nanotechnology in life sciences. *J Nanomaterials*. 2022;2022:3083728. doi:10.1155/2022/3083728
23. Singh D, Tiwary AK, Bedi N. Self-microemulsifying drug delivery system for problematic molecules: an update. *Recent Pat Nanotechnol*. 2019;13(2):92–113. doi:10.2174/1872210513666190619102521
24. Desale SL, Deshmukh AS, Mahajan VR. Solubility enhancement of poorly water-soluble drug fenofibrate by inclusion complex. *World J Pharmacol Res Technol*. 2015;4(3):242–255
25. Bind A, Das S, Singh VD, Kumar R, Chourasia A, Saha P. Natural bioactives for the potential management of gastric ulceration. *Turk J Physiother Rehabil*. 2020;32(3):221–226
26. Abuzar SM, Hyun SM, Kim JH, Park HJ, Kim MS, Park JS, Hwang SJ. Enhancing the solubility and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs using supercritical antisolvent (SAS) process. *Int J Pharm*. 2018;538(1–2):1–13. doi:10.1016/j.ijpharm.2017.12.041
27. Campardelli R, Baldino L, Reverchon E. Supercritical fluids applications in nanomedicine. *J Supercrit Fluids*. 2015;101:193–214. doi:10.1016/j.supflu.2015.01.030
28. Zhang Y, Wang S, Dai M, Nai J, Zhu L, Sheng H. Solubility and bioavailability enhancement of oridonin: a review. *Molecules*. 2020;25(2):332. doi:10.3390/molecules25020332
29. Sharma KS, Sahoo J, Agrawal S, Kumari A. Solid dispersions: a technology for improving bioavailability. *J Anal Pharm Res*. 2019;8(4):127–133. doi:10.15406/japlr.2019.08.00326
30. Veni DK, Gupta NV. Development and evaluation of Eudragit coated environmental sensitive solid lipid nanoparticles using central composite design module for enhancement of oral bioavailability of linagliptin. *Int J Polym Mater Polym Biomaterials*. 2019;69(7):407–418. doi:10.1080/00914037.2019.1570513
31. Malkawi R, Malkawi WI, Al-Mahmoud Y, Tawalbeh J. Current trends on solid dispersions: past, present, and future. *Adv Pharmacol Pharm Sci*. 2022;2022:5916013. doi:10.1155/2022/5916013
32. Patel BB, Patel JK, Chakraborty S, Shukla D. Revealing facts behind spray dried solid dispersion technology used for solubility enhancement. *Saudi Pharm J*. 2015;23(4):352–365. doi:10.1016/j.jsps.2013.12.013
33. O'Donnell PB, McGinity JW. Preparation of microspheres by the solvent evaporation technique. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev*. 1997;28(1):25–42. doi:10.1016/S0169-409X(97)00049-5
34. Khansary MA, Shirazian S, Walker G. Molecular engineering of co-crystallization process in hot melt extrusion based on kinetics of elementary molecular processes. *Int J Pharm*. 2021;601:120495. doi:10.1016/j.ijpharm.2021.120495
35. Dhapte V, Mehta P. Advances in hydrotropic solutions: an updated review. *St Petersburg Polytech Univ J Phys Math*. 2015;1(4):424–435. doi:10.1016/j.spjpm.2015.12.006
36. Mahapatra APK, Patil V, Patil R. Solubility enhancement of poorly soluble drugs by using novel techniques: a comprehensive review. *Int J Pharm Tech Res*. 2020;13(2):80–93. doi:10.20902/IJPTR.2019.130211
37. Kumar S, Singh P. Various techniques for solubility enhancement: an overview. *Pharma Innov J*. 2016;5(1):23–28
38. Sekiguchi K, Obi N. Studies on absorption of eutectic mixture. I. A comparison of the behavior of eutectic mixture of sulphathiazole and that of ordinary sulphathiazole in man. *Chem Pharm Bull (Tokyo)*. 1961;9:866–872. doi:10.1248/cpb.9.866
39. Goldberg DS, Vijayalakshmi N, Swaan PW, Ghandehari H. G3.5 PAMAM dendrimers enhance transepithelial transport of SN38 while minimizing gastrointestinal toxicity. *J Control Release*. 2011;150(3):318–325. doi:10.1016/j.jconrel.2010.11.022

40. Dhirendra K, Lewis S, Udupa N, Atin K. Solid dispersions: a review. Pak J Pharm Sci. 2009;22(2):234–246

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